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Development of an Autonomous Vehicle System with Remote Control and Cybersecurity Features

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ABSTRACT

The transformation of transportation technologies has evolved from mechanical innovations to intelligent and connected mobility solutions. One of the most prominent examples of this transformation is autonomous driving systems, which offer significant benefits in terms of safety, comfort, and efficiency. However, their reliance on digital components such as wireless communication and remote access also introduces serious cybersecurity risks. In particular, mobile applications developed for vehicle control create new attack surfaces on connected systems. This study aims to develop a prototype autonomous vehicle system equipped with integrated cybersecurity features and managed via a mobile application that operates over a wireless network. Various cyberattacks—such as Deauthentication, Man-in-the-Middle, unauthorized remote access, and False Data Injection—were simulated under conditions approximating real-world scenarios, and the resulting network traffic data was collected. This data was then analyzed using machine learning techniques to automate the detection of attacks. The findings demonstrate the effectiveness of various algorithms, such as Naive Bayes, k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN), Random Forest, and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), in detecting different types of attacks. Notably, the kNN algorithm stood out as the most successful model, exhibiting superior performance across various metrics, including accuracy, F1 score, and test time. This study highlights that not only the driving capabilities of autonomous vehicles but also their cybersecurity infrastructures must be enhanced using artificial intelligence-based methods. The developed system offers a model architecture that encompasses both connected mobility solutions and security, providing a solid foundation for future autonomous transportation technologies.

1 INTRODUCTION

Today, technological advancements are driving significant transformations in transportation systems, making them more innovative, more efficient, and user-friendly. One of the core components of this transformation is autonomous vehicle technology, which not only enables driverless mobility but also contributes to multiple objectives such as improving traffic safety, increasing energy efficiency, and promoting environmental sustainability by reducing fossil fuel consumption. Autonomous driving systems utilize integrated sensors, control units, and artificial intelligence algorithms to perceive their surroundings and perform driving tasks without human intervention. At the foundation of these technological systems lie remote access and control capabilities provided through internet connectivity, wireless communication protocols, and mobile applications.

However, this advanced level of connectivity and data-driven control architecture also introduces serious cybersecurity threats. By design, autonomous vehicles are vulnerable to various types of cyberattacks. Unauthorized access, Deauthentication, Man-in-the-Middle (MitM), and particularly False Data Injection (FDI) attacks can be executed by malicious actors, jeopardizing passenger safety and undermining system reliability. FDI attacks, in particular, involve injecting fabricated data into the vehicle's sensor or control systems, causing it to react based on false information, which can potentially lead to incorrect decision-making processes and result in accidents or navigation errors. Such attacks are perilous due to their capacity to manipulate the AI- and data-driven decision mechanisms of autonomous systems.

In this study, a prototype autonomous vehicle capable of wireless control was developed, and both conventional and advanced cyberattack scenarios were applied to the system. Simulated attacks, including deauthentication, Man-in-the-Middle, unauthorized remote access, and False Data Injection, were used to identify system vulnerabilities. Additionally, we propose a simulation architecture for FDI using synthetic data injections and system response analysis, as a step towards implementing real-time detection in future versions. The network traffic data collected during these simulations was analyzed using machine learning methods to evaluate the feasibility of automated attack detection. The findings underscore the necessity of designing autonomous vehicle systems not only to withstand physical threats but also to resist digital threats. In this regard, the study proposes a modular and cyber-resilient platform architecture.

2 LITERATURE

The growing integration of connectivity and automation in modern vehicles has significantly elevated cybersecurity concerns in the domain of autonomous driving. Autonomous vehicles (AVs), acting as cyber-physical systems, are particularly vulnerable to attacks that exploit their networked components and AI-driven decision-making processes. As emphasized by Pali et al. [1], autonomous vehicles (AVs) are integral to the development of future smart cities. Still, they remain highly vulnerable to cyber threats due to their reliance on communication technologies such as 5G, IoT, and SDN. These technologies, while enabling real-time decision-making, also expand the attack surface.

Javidi Niroumand et al. [2] provide a comprehensive classification of cyber-physical attacks on connected and autonomous vehicles (CAVs), proposing mitigation strategies rooted in control theory. The study highlights that AVs face vulnerabilities at multiple layers—sensors, ECUs, and communication links—which can be exploited through Man-in-the-Middle, False Data Injection (FDI), or Denial-of-Service (DoS) attacks.

Chattopadhyay et al. emphasized the necessity of embedding "security by design" into AV systems, highlighting the limitations of traditional IT defense models when applied to complex autonomous frameworks that interact with both physical and digital infrastructure [1]. Similarly, Girdhar et al. reviewed adversarial machine learning threats targeting deep learning components within AVs, particularly computer vision systems, and stressed the importance of explainable AI in mitigating these risks [3].

Abreu et al. conducted a systematic review across 111 peer-reviewed studies, categorizing security controls into themes such as blockchain, intrusion detection systems (IDS), and V2X communications. Their findings revealed substantial gaps, particularly the underutilization of Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) systems and real-world validation methods [4].

Durlik et al. examined common attack surfaces, including remote hacking, sensor manipulation, and DoS attacks. They identified key limitations in AV defense strategies, such as latency constraints and a lack of standardization, and advocated for AI-enhanced and blockchain-supported protection mechanisms [5]. Likewise, Sudheer Kumar et al. analyzed the cybersecurity risks of sensors like LiDAR and cameras, noting their susceptibility to spoofing and glare attacks, which can impair AV perception and control [6].

Axelrod's analysis of systems-of-systems architectures exposed how fragmented development across vehicle, infrastructure, and ride-hailing systems expands attack surfaces and complicates coordinated defense efforts. He argued for enforceable global standards to ensure cross-system integrity [7]. Morad and Yako, focusing on V2V message spoofing, emphasized the potential of AI-driven anomaly detection in maintaining reliable and trustworthy vehicular communication [8]. Algarni and Thayanathan introduced a 6G-based intelligent cybersecurity framework tailored to dynamic threat landscapes. Their model integrates cryptography with AI decision-making to proactively neutralize attacks on AV systems [9]. Razali brings a unique perspective by situating these threats in the context of big data analytics within CAVs. His work emphasizes how centralized data aggregation, cloud vulnerabilities, and adversarial machine learning all escalate risk profiles. Razali proposes stochastic risk modeling, game-theoretic equilibrium frameworks, and adaptive intrusion detection as countermeasures. His formulation of cyber risk over time using stochastic differential equations further anchors the discussion in mathematically grounded risk quantification [10].

Collectively, these studies demonstrate a convergence toward AI- and communication-based security models for AVs, emphasizing proactive, integrated, and adaptive strategies. Future research should prioritize large-scale real-world testing, policy standardization, and human-centered design to ensure both safety and trust in AV ecosystems.

In contrast to the studies above, this work presents the design and implementation of a Raspberry Pi-based autonomous vehicle prototype integrated with real-time wireless control and AI-assisted cybersecurity mechanisms. Furthermore, it differentiates itself by combining physical prototype testing with embedded lightweight AI models, something rarely demonstrated in related literature. Unlike prior research that primarily focuses on theoretical frameworks or simulated environments, this study experimentally evaluates the impacts of Deauthentication, Man-in-the-Middle, DoS, and False Data Injection attacks on an operational physical system. Network traffic data collected during these attacks is analyzed using multiple machine learning algorithms, and the most effective model, k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN), is embedded into the system for real-time intrusion detection. Thus, this research contributes a practical, lightweight, and modular approach to enhancing the cyber-resilience of resource-constrained autonomous platforms in real-world scenarios.

3 EXPERIMENTATION AND ANALYSIS

This section presents the autonomous vehicle system developed within the scope of this study, the cyberattacks conducted on the experimental setup shown in Figure 1, and the detailed detection and outcomes of these attacks.

Figure 1. Autonomous Vehicle Prototype

Figure 2. System Network Topology

The autonomous vehicle platform developed in this study is primarily equipped with software-based driving assistance systems and is designed to exhibit autonomous movement under specific environmental conditions. The system generates situational awareness by processing data from camera images and ultrasonic sensors, which are evaluated through algorithms running on an embedded processor (Raspberry Pi) to control direction, speed, and braking mechanisms. This is achieved via the network topology shown in Figure 2.

The onboard camera captures real-time images of the road surface and transfers them to image processing algorithms, which are based on Python and OpenCV. Lane markings and directional cues are identified from the images, and the required steering angle for lane keeping is computed. The lane-following algorithm analyzes the vehicle's current position and orientation, issuing corrective commands when deviations occur, thereby enabling autonomous navigation without human intervention.

Additionally, the system is capable of detecting environmental objects. Ultrasonic sensors mounted on the front of the vehicle continuously measure the distance to nearby obstacles. If the distance falls below a predefined threshold, an automatic braking mechanism is triggered in real time, serving as a safety layer to reduce collision risk.

Thanks to the synchronized operation of all components, the system performs core autonomous driving tasks such as lane tracking and obstacle avoidance using low-cost hardware, making it feasible for academic and prototype-level implementations. This architecture has been developed to test the

fundamental principles of autonomous driving technologies experimentally and to evaluate various cybersecurity scenarios in real-time.

Figure 3. Line Detection Algorithm Diagram.

Figure 4. Ultrasonic Sensor Diagram

Figure 5. Object Recognition Diagram

Figures 3, 4, and 5 illustrate the data processing flows of the three primary perception layers of the developed system. The first diagram illustrates the sequential steps of the lane-tracking algorithm, which is based on camera-driven image processing. This process begins with preprocessing live images (grayscale conversion, blurring), followed by Canny edge detection and Region of Interest (ROI) masking, culminating in Hough Transform-based lane line detection. The deviation angle between the vehicle’s current position and the lane center is then calculated, and the steering direction

is adjusted accordingly. This process is repeated for every video frame to ensure continuous lane tracking.

The second diagram depicts the decision flow of the ultrasonic sensor-based collision prevention system. After acquiring distance measurements, data validity is checked and compared against a safety threshold to ensure accuracy and reliability. If a critical distance violation is detected, an emergency braking command is generated, and a log entry is created to maintain system integrity.

The third diagram demonstrates the pipeline of the YOLO (You Only Look Once)-based deep learning algorithm integrated for real-time object detection. Each video frame is normalized and processed by the YOLO model to identify objects within the scene. Detected objects are then communicated to other system modules, enhancing environmental awareness and supporting autonomous decision-making.

3.1 Attack System Preparation

Cyberattacks, including Deauthentication, DoS, and Man-in-the-Middle (MitM), were executed on the system using various tools available on the Kali Linux platform, such as Nmap, hping3, airodump-ng, aireplay-ng, Ettercap, bettercap, and Wireshark. These attacks were performed on the network topology illustrated in Figure 6, following the scenario steps shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6. Attacker Network Topology

Figure 7. Attack Flow Diagram

To evaluate the resilience of the developed autonomous system against cybersecurity threats, a five-stage testing and analysis model was implemented. This structure was designed to assess system responses to different threat types and develop a comprehensive security architecture. Rather than simulating all attacks directly, the flow diagram provides a systematic framework covering both actual and conceptual threats.

3.1.1 Discovery Phase

This phase involved network scanning to identify connected system components, open ports, and IP addresses. It served as the initial step in attack surface mapping, laying the groundwork for subsequent scenarios.

3.1.2 Attack Phase

Several attack scenarios were implemented to explore potential network vulnerabilities:

- **Deauthentication Attack:** Aimed to disrupt the connection between the system and the controller by forcibly disconnecting the wireless link.
- **Man-in-the-Middle (MitM) Attack:** Intercepted and manipulated data traffic between the client and the system.
- **False Data Injection (FDI) Attack:** Conceptually analyzed in this study. This attack involves deliberately altering sensor data to mislead decision-making algorithms, particularly those based on critical inputs, such as distance sensors.

3.1.3 Detection Phase

During the attacks, network traffic was thoroughly analyzed using anomaly detection techniques. Additionally, future iterations of the system will incorporate layered defense mechanisms, including encryption and authentication modules for end-to-end data protection. Machine learning classifiers were trained to distinguish between regular and attack traffic. While no AI-based detection

model was implemented for FDI in this phase, the theoretical applicability of such models was discussed.

3.1.4 Monitoring Phase

System and network components were continuously monitored in real-time scenarios. Behavior and response times following attacks were analyzed, providing groundwork for potential automated detection and response mechanisms.

3.1.5 Notification Phase

The system was designed to generate logs and notify administrators when a threat is detected. Basic notification mechanisms were planned to alert users without requiring direct system intervention.

This structure combines practical security testing with theoretical modeling, enabling a comprehensive security assessment that extends beyond the types of implemented attacks.

4 ATTACK DETECTION

In this study, data obtained from network traffic were analyzed using various artificial intelligence-based algorithms to detect potential cyberattacks. The developed intrusion detection model consists of four main stages. In the first stage, preprocessing steps were applied to the raw traffic data, including the handling of missing values, conversion of features into appropriate formats, and segmentation into 10-millisecond time intervals to achieve a structured and analyzable format. In the second stage, the dataset was split into 66% training and 34% testing sets, and classification operations were performed. Four different machine learning algorithms—Naive Bayes, k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN), Random Forest, and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) Neural Network—were used to evaluate system performance. A 10-fold cross-validation method was employed to enhance the reliability of the results.

In the third stage, model performance was assessed using metrics such as accuracy, F1-score, precision, recall, Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC), and Area Under the Curve (AUC); results were supported with visual tools to enable inter-model comparisons. However, to mitigate overfitting risks, additional validations and regularization methods will be explored in future deployments. In the final stage, the algorithm that achieved the highest overall performance was selected for real-time application and integrated into the system.

As shown in Table 1, accuracy alone is not sufficient to evaluate the effectiveness of AI-based algorithms. Complementary performance metrics such as F1-score, precision, recall, MCC, and ROC-AUC are critical for a holistic assessment of the system. Moreover, time-based variables such as testing duration play a significant role in real-time systems.

The analysis revealed that the k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) algorithm demonstrated the most balanced and effective performance, with an accuracy of 98.76%, an F1-score of 98.76%, a precision of 98.78%, and a recall of 98.76%. Additionally, the MCC value was calculated as 0.9787, and the ROC-AUC score reached 0.9943. These results indicate that kNN not only achieved high accuracy but also provided strong metrics reflecting overall classification quality.

Based on these findings, the k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) algorithm was selected for attack detection within the expert system. To address kNN's computational limitations, potential enhancements such as KD-Trees, dimensionality reduction, and instance pruning are discussed as

part of future work. Due to its relatively short training time and high success rates, kNN offers an effective and reliable solution for detecting attacks in network traffic.

Table 1. Model Comparison

Model	Train Time (s)	Test Time (s)	CA	F1	Precision	Recall	MCC	AUC
kNN	2.10	399.6185	0.9876	0.9876	0.9878	0.9876	0.9787	0.9943
Random Forest	26.85	1.5448	0.9873	0.9873	0.9875	0.9873	0.9782	0.9973
Neural Network	869.254	0.2219	0.9865	0.9866	0.9867	0.9865	0.9769	0.9973
Naive Bayes	0.22	0.1294	0.8305	0.8306	0.8677	0.8305	0.7265	0.9827

5 CONCLUSION

The advancement of autonomous vehicle technologies necessitates not only mechanical and software innovations but also comprehensive security measures. In this study, a prototype autonomous vehicle system, controllable via a mobile application with wireless communication capabilities, was developed and integrated with cybersecurity mechanisms. Various attack scenarios simulating real-world conditions—including Deauthentication, Man-in-the-Middle, unauthorized access, and False Data Injection—were executed on the system. The resulting network traffic data was analyzed using machine learning algorithms to detect such threats.

The experimental results showed that algorithms such as k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN), Random Forest, and Neural Networks achieved high detection accuracy in identifying cyberattacks. Among them, the kNN algorithm stood out due to its short training time and high performance. However, given that kNN relies on comparing each test instance with all training samples, it may result in an increased computational load when handling large datasets. Therefore, in time-critical applications, algorithm selection should carefully consider the trade-off between speed and accuracy.

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of AI-driven solutions for automatically detecting cyber threats in connected vehicle systems. Furthermore, the implementation of field-based attack scenarios confirms that the proposed security models are viable under real-world conditions. However, a specialized artificial intelligence model for False Data Injection (FDI) attacks has not yet been developed within the scope of this research. FDI threats were examined at a conceptual level and interpreted using anomaly detection approaches. Future research should focus on designing detection systems tailored to FDI and similar complex threat types to enhance the system's cyber resilience further.

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